

Recommended citation: Kovács, P. (2019). The Medvematek Project and the Smart Trails application. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 2059-2060). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657311.

THE *MEDVEMATEK* PROJECT AND THE SMART TRAILS APPLICATION

P. Kovács

Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary

A Matematika Összeköt Egyesület, Hungary

MTA-BME Information Systems Research Group

Topics: How to detect and attract talents with new generations of learning technologies and networks; Fundamentals of Engineering Education: Mathematics and Physics

Keywords: talent development, gamification, mobile application, mathematics

In our modern times there are a couple of core skills, namely problem solving skills, capability for teamwork, adaptability etc., which every engineer needs throughout their life. Some of these skills have to be nurtured from a young age, especially since the necessity of complex and scientific thinking scares many teenagers away from an engineering career. The prejudice against school subjects that develop logical and solution-based thinking (such as mathematics) poses a real problem, as it limits the number of capable students, even against the goals of the industry and the actors of higher education, who seek to train ever more professionals in these fields.

The *Medvematek* Project aims to address these issues by a comprehensive program that gets children involved as early as the age of 10, and follows their development into their university studies. Through innovative tools we engage teenagers with outside the school activities that build upon positive experiences, thus catching their interest and raising the likeliness that they will later choose a path in higher education related to mathematics, engineering or similar fields. At the same time we nurture their core skills and develop a community among them, which can form the basis of a professional network in the future. The *Medvematek* Project reaches around 15000 students annually at its outdoor problem-solving competitions, a series of maths camps and other innovative community-building events.

The most successful of these events are the outdoor problem-solving competitions, during which teams compete against each other, while trying to navigate a map at the same time. These take place in public parks, where we set up a set of stations. Each team is given a starting station, where they need to solve a puzzle and depending on the outcome (i.e. whether the solution is correct), they are sent to a next station. Once they solve enough problems correctly, they complete the track. However incorrect solutions lead to penalties, increasing both the distance needed to walk and the number of problems needed to solve. These rules, combined with the fact that good solutions lead to rewards along the way, keep the teenagers engaged and apply the pedagogical mindset of gamification to build a fun activity.

The Smart Trails application is a mobile app developed by the same team responsible for the *Medvematek* Project. It was designed to provide an experience in the same mold as the outdoors competitions. The application replicates the playful activity of completing tracks by problem-solving for the students or the teams of students using it, without the necessity of volunteers manning the stations along the way. The application allows for the creation of the trails teams need to follow with a varying complexity of the graph structure behind the (possibly virtual) maps. It also provides QR-codes which can be printed out to create an actual, physical track as well as the possibility of logging the results from the teachers' side. For the teams the application reveals the problems needed to solve at every station after reading the QR-codes and directions to the next waypoint.

At the beginning of the workshop we will introduce the *Medvematek* Project shortly, in order to allow participants to discover the pedagogical and methodological benefits of our approach. The introduction will be extended to the Smart Trails application, discussing how it enables the same concepts to emerge in teaching practice. During the workshop participants will get a chance to familiarize themselves with the application, both by trying out an exhibition track which we will prepare and by getting to design tracks of their own. Volunteers from the *Medvematek* Project will help them out in these activities, opening the possibility to discuss questions which might emerge during the time. Therefore, along the way the participants will get a chance to learn the capabilities of an application that can serve as an out-of-the-box examination tool or applied to organize fun events, which engage possible future students. We welcome everybody to the session, who is interested in new ways to raise the interest of students in the fields of STEM.